

Green Entrepreneurship, Economic Opportunities, and Sustainable Development in Kogi State

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ABSTRACT

The work examines the place of green entrepreneurship in the creation of economic opportunities and enhancement of sustainable development in Kogi State. Apparently, unemployment is one of the major burning social realities confronting the Nigerian nation and Kogi State in particular in recent years. In other words, as a result of overpopulation and bad governance, among other factors, lack of economic opportunities and unemployment have become chronic and intractable in the country in recent years. These challenges, on the other hand, have been the brain behind the youth restiveness facing the people. On the other hand, climate change has, over the years, exposed the human race to different challenges, thereby calling for innovative means of managing the menace. World over, an effort to creatively manage the aforementioned challenge, which is otherwise known as green entrepreneurship, has created economic opportunities and strengthened the economy of many nations of the world. It is based on this backdrop that this research is undertaken. Utilising a qualitative research methodology, including key in-depth interviews, the study examined the abovementioned issues. The theoretical underpinning is drawn from the Green and Sustainable Business Models, highlighting the potential of green entrepreneurship in creating economic opportunities and enhancing sustainable development. The study underscores the importance of green entrepreneurship in creating economic opportunities, proposing that effective practice of green entrepreneurship can generate momentous economic benefits. The findings advocate for strategic efforts by local and state governments to promote green entrepreneurship in order to attain a viable and sustainable economic framework.

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1.1. Introduction

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation and largest economy, stands at a critical juncture in its development trajectory. Despite its abundant human and natural resources, the country continues to confront persistent challenges such as widespread poverty, infrastructural deficits, insecurity, weak institutions, and environmental degradation. These structural and systemic constraints have impeded progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and pose significant threats to achieving sustainable national development. The urgency of addressing these issues has intensified, particularly as Nigeria navigates post-pandemic recovery, global energy transitions, and escalating climate change risks (Oweibia, Elemuwa, Akpan, et al., 2024).

However, it has been noted that, in the last three to four decades, environmental issues have dominated both local and international discussions. The role the environment plays in the developmental process of any nation cannot be relegated to the background. The environment, apart from being the physical surroundings for natural habitats, also provides the basis for human exploits in agricultural, technological, industrial, commercial, and tourism development of a society, among others. No wonder environmental issues now occupy centre stage in academic discourse and other public fora, both at the national and international levels. (Mark, 2021).

Nikolaou, *et al.* (2018) observed that environmental issues did not gain official recognition until the 1988 Koko toxic waste dumping saga, which brought to the fore the need to establish the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA), Federal Ministry of Environment and other relevant agencies in Nigeria to tackle environmentally related issues in the country. Issues such as environmental pollution, sanitation, depletion of the ozone layer, desertification, flooding, erosion, poverty, bush burning, deforestation, soil conservation and so on.

The above backdrop also paves the way for the coining of the term green entrepreneurship. Green entrepreneurship refers to a special subset of entrepreneurship that aims at creating and implementing solutions to environmental problems and promoting social change so that the environment is not harmed. It has also been suggested that green entrepreneurship could be a new business paradigm instead of a subset of entrepreneurship because green entrepreneurs have wider motivations than just launching eco-friendly products and services for a niche market (Kirkwood and Walton, 2010). As has been mentioned earlier, the Nigerian nation and Kogi State in particular have been confronted with climate-related challenges and economic issues such as unemployment, among others. This work interrogates the potential of green entrepreneurship in managing the issues.

1.2. Results

Green and Sustainable Business Models

Green and sustainable business models are crucial for creating eco-friendly, sustainable businesses. As Teece (200, p. 179) defines, “a business model describes the design or architecture of the value creation, delivery and capture mechanisms employed”. Green business models may include the value destruction of existing business models as well as new ways to create and capture value (Roome and Louche, 2016).

With the sustainability requirements, businesses need to develop innovative ideas and business models and not just add superficial fixes to current non-sustainable solutions (Bocken *et al.* 2014). If companies improve their energy efficiency, but simultaneously their production and sales grow as a result of enhanced affordability, the companies are generating a rebound effect. This means that even though companies develop their eco-design and eco-efficiency, it is not necessarily decreasing their resource usage, and there is a negative impact of the products on the environment due to the increasing sales and demand in the markets (Bocken *et al.* 2014). The focus in green companies should be on creating more durable and repairable products, and thus, the revenue would be collected from sources other than just sales of products.

Sustainable and green business model creation is multidisciplinary, and different kinds of stakeholders need to be involved from the very early phases. A business model usually has three main components: the value proposition, the value creation and delivery, and the value capture (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). In a green and sustainable business model, the economic, environmental and social levels of the business need to be included, and different kinds of stakeholders need to be involved from the three levels of the business environment (Bocken *et al.* 2014).

Truly sustainable and green business models need to consider the full life-cycle of the products, including the end-of-life stage. When innovating a new sustainable and green business model, companies can focus, for example, on these specific aspects to create value in new ways and possibly extend the product life and sustainability of the product (Bocken *et al.*, 2014):

- Maximise material efficiency and energy efficiency;
- Use waste to create value;
- Substitute virgin materials with renewables and use natural processes;
- Create and offer functionality instead of ownership of products;
- Encourage the principle of sufficiency;
- Re-design the business for the benefit of society/environment.

Typically, green entrepreneurship is favoured in such fields where the lifestyles, health and safety aspects of the customers are considered to be very important. Here are a few examples from different industrial sectors:

Ecotourism: The way tourism impacts the lives of locals has led to the development of ecotourism ventures where the target is that the local environment and communities benefit from the tourism business (Scheyvens, 1999). The target of some tourists is to see rare animal species, which does not help to develop an appreciation for biodiversity. However, with ecotourism, the target is the conservation of threatened natural habitats and species. The active participation of the local community is crucial for the success of ecotourism so that the numbers and distribution of tourists are controlled and managed effectively in the local environment and nature, the ecotourism initiatives may fail to be sustainable (Krüger, 2005).

Concept of Green Entrepreneurship

Green entrepreneurship can be explained based on theories on entrepreneurship, and environmental and welfare economics as a subset of sustainable entrepreneurship (Dean and McMullen, 2007). The environmental economics literature states that environmental degradation is a result of market failures, while the entrepreneurship literature claims that there are business opportunities in market failure (Dean and McMullen, 2007).

The target of green entrepreneurship is to improve the business ecosystems where businesses operate and, at the same time, promote changes in business practices that have an impact on the natural environment and society (Gast *et al.*, 2017).

This can be on the level of business and production processes and/or products themselves. Green entrepreneurship is responding to the growing demands for the termination of environmentally degrading businesses and consumers' growing willingness to pay for the reduction of activities that have a negative impact on the environment. Green entrepreneurs are seizing business opportunities that can result in the improvement of ecological sustainability (Dean and McMullen, 2007).

It is important to note that certain differences exist between conventional entrepreneurship and green entrepreneurship. The main difference between conventional entrepreneurship and green entrepreneurship is the value creation logic. Conventional entrepreneurship contributes to economic growth and regional development (Suresh and Ramraj, 2012; Shane, and Venkataraman, 2000) and can develop local economies (Audretsch and Pena-Legazkue, 2012).

Green entrepreneurship refers to businesses that have the target to minimise the business's impact on the natural environment, i.e. take into account the ecological dimension of sustainability (Gast *et al.* 2017).

In conventional entrepreneurship, the main and often sole driver is economic value creation, while in green entrepreneurship, the economic aspect is considered as a means to achieving also other values on the environmental and social levels (Dean and McMullen, 2007; Vuorio *et al.* 2017). In addition to the economic perspectives, conventional entrepreneurs are also more and more answering to the sustainability requirements coming from environmental legislation as well as consumer demand for more green products. However, the factors that make an entrepreneur green, in addition to the financial performance, are the environmental dimension in the core business strategy and that business opportunities are seized in order to eliminate the harm done to the natural environment (Cohen and Winn, 2007).

There are various terms used currently in the literature to refer to a similar field of study as 'green entrepreneurship', such as 'ecopreneurship', 'eco-entrepreneurship', and 'environmental entrepreneurship', and the terms can even be used in the same contexts (Schaper, 2016). Green entrepreneurship is already a well-known concept, even though it is a rather new field of academic research. In the academic literature, several concepts and different terminology are used to describe entrepreneurship and innovations that aim at reducing negative influences on the environment. In the 1970's, there were already some initial studies, but in the late 80's and 90's, this field started to grow (Schaper, 2016). In the 1990's, Bennett (1991), Berle (1991) and Blue (1990) were the first to refer to the concepts of 'environmental entrepreneur', 'green entrepreneur', 'eco-entrepreneur' and 'ecopreneur'. 'Green', 'eco', 'environmental' and 'sustainable' are all used in the same contexts, and the definitions are very similar, the only difference being that the term 'sustainable' also strongly incorporates social aspects as well as economic and environmental ones (Zubeltzu-Jaka *et al.* 2018).

Sustainable entrepreneurship includes value creation on three different levels: the economic, social and environmental, but there may also be some cases where social entrepreneurs do not pursue economic gain (Dean and McMullen, 2007; Vuorio *et al.* 2017).

In the same vein, there are certain characteristics of green entrepreneurs. These characteristics formed the factors that are distinctive for green entrepreneurs. The factors are:

- First of all, they are entrepreneurs and thus run businesses that involve some risk, and they are looking for new business opportunities that can be developed and grown into viable businesses.
- Second, green entrepreneurs have business practices that have a positive impact on the environment, and they operate with such principles that their operations do not harm or have a neutral impact on the environment.
- Third, green entrepreneurs operate in eco-friendly ways due to their personal intrinsic values and motivation, and are thus intentionally being environmentally conscious in their business. Thus, green entrepreneurs can be considered as environmental problem solvers that are also acting as social change agents to change the practices and consumption habits in society (Schaper, 2016; Farinelli, 2011). The term green entrepreneur can be used to refer to individuals or groups who are acting as green entrepreneurs either in organisations or firms (de Bruin 2016). It is added that green entrepreneurs can be divided into two main categories on the basis of the types of drivers they are acting upon. The definition of green entrepreneurs can be considered to be a wide one, including both individuals with strong green values and principles of sustainability, in addition to opportunists who are taking advantage of a green niche market (Walley and Taylor, 2002).

Some green entrepreneurs are impacted by the institutional context in society, and the need for change, some by ideology, and other green entrepreneurs are targeting strategic and competitive advantage through their sustainable innovations (Nikolaou et al., 2018). The motivation of green entrepreneurs to pursue sustainable ventures can thus be either opportunity-driven or sustainability-driven: opportunity-driven entrepreneurs aim at building a profitable business venture and use sustainability as a business opportunity for gaining profit; sustainability-driven entrepreneurs aim to contribute to sustainability, and thus a profitable business is a means for achieving this (Parrish, 2010).

The basic assumption, also about green entrepreneurs, is that they all have certain levels of economic profit objectives if they are not working in the non-profit sector (e.g., voluntary or public-sector organisations). It has also been found that green entrepreneurs can have a mixed set of motives consisting of green, ethical and social motives (Walley and Taylor, 2002). The typology for differentiating green entrepreneurs can be further presented with four main types: innovative opportunists, visionary champions, ethical mavericks and ad hoc enviropreneurs (Walley and Taylor, 2002).

Green entrepreneurs have similar motives for becoming entrepreneurs as conventional entrepreneurs. Green entrepreneurs are motivated by: personal green values, making a living, their passion, being the boss, and seeing an opportunity in the markets; however, their financial motivations are often on a lower level than those of conventional entrepreneurs (Kirkwood and Walton, 2010). O'Neill and Gibbs (2016) found that green

entrepreneurs saw themselves as different from the mainstream and their views had more in common with degrowth principles and the need to redefine prosperity.

Green Entrepreneurship, Economic Opportunities and Sustainable Development in Kogi State

The work employs the key in-depth interview approach of the qualitative methodology to carry out its findings. Through this method, relevant respondents drawn from selected areas of Lokoja, Kogi State capital, were interacted with on the issues under the study. Their responses were content-analyzed along side related existing literature. According to one of the respondents, Suleiman Hassan (Key In-depth Interview, 04/01/2026), green entrepreneurship has great potential to create economic opportunities for our teeming unemployed, thereby enhancing sustainable development of the state.

Amina Adams (Key In-depth Interview, 04/01/2026) supported that green entrepreneurship remains one of the possible ways to attain sustainable development in today's world. For instance, it involves renewable energy, and investments in renewable energy reduce energy costs while also reducing environmental waste. Hence, it has the potential to promote sustainable development in the state.

Abenedego Roseline (Key In-depth Interview, 04/01/2026) added that green entrepreneurs have the potential to create new jobs. Sectors that focus on sustainable practices may demand more labour than traditional sectors. This makes it important in Kogi State, which is battling to manage the complex issues of unemployment. In John Awudu's opinion (Key In-depth Interview, 04/01/2026), for sustainable economic growth to be achieved in Kogi State, there is an urgent call to investigate and get to the root of environmental issues such as climate change, waste disposal, pollution, the depletion of non-renewable natural resources such as petroleum, natural gas and energy shortage bringing out innovative measures to tackle these challenges facing the state and other parts of the country. This echoes the thrust of the Green and Sustainable Business Models, and at the same time agrees with the positions of a number of scholars on the issue. It has been observed that green entrepreneurs are very important currently to the development of the economy because they help to create new jobs by introducing sustainable innovations on the markets and responding to the demands for change in society (Farinelli et al.; 2011; Silajdžić et al. 2015). Green entrepreneurs can be considered to be change agents and drivers of sustainability and social change (de Bruin, 2016). They can also be considered to be very personally involved and connected to the development of their business, as they support environmental values and have social awareness even before considering the economic aspects of their business (Silajdžić *et al.* 2015).

In addition to green entrepreneurship being important for recognising new eco-friendly business opportunities, it has a critical role in transforming the existing business paradigm into a more sustainable direction so that the environmental and social perspectives are taken into account in addition to the pure economic gains (Schaper, 2016; 2002). Green entrepreneurship is needed from a development perspective, as global inequality, increasing unemployment numbers, destruction of wildlife and impacts of climate change are threatening society and natural ecosystems. By

supporting the development of green enterprises and thus improving the resilience of economies and natural ecosystems, the promotion of green entrepreneurship is in line with the global environmental targets, e.g., the Rio+20 Conference (Farinelli et al., 2011), as well as the UN sustainable development goals.

The transition in society towards a more sustainable system must be done in cooperation between actors in different fields of technology, policy, economics, business, as well as on the markets, which requires a wider perspective than in conventional entrepreneurship (Geels, 2011). Green entrepreneurs are individuals who combine their environmental awareness with an entrepreneurial endeavour and thus are crucial actors in society's and economy's transformation into a 'more sustainable business paradigm' (Schaper, 2002; Gibbs and O'Neill, 2014).

When an industry is transforming to become more sustainable or green, the market incumbents (or firms that are dominating the markets) get feedback from their stakeholders that they should develop their processes and products to be more sustainable. As incumbents are tied to their existing resources and capabilities, the transformation can be slow and only incremental (Hockerts and Wüstenhagen, 2010). This makes it hard for the incumbents to transform into green entrepreneurs in the case of existing products that they may already be producing, but in the case of new green product development, incumbents may be more successful in competing with green entrepreneurs who are newcomers on the market as well (Hockerts and Wüstenhagen, 2010).

Green construction: Green construction includes principles of environmental impact, resource management and recycling implementation (Ishak, Kamal and Yusof, 2017). The usage of green building materials in construction can help to minimise the production of waste and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Lam et al. (2009) identified five factors of green construction: (1) green technology and techniques, (2) reliability and quality of specification, (3) leadership and responsibility, (4) stakeholder involvement, and (5) guidance and benchmarking systems.

Eco-friendly fashion retailing: Green retailing refers to retailing products with environmental benefits. The global demand for green products has resulted in major global retailers creating labels that claim environmental benefits (green labels), and indices to evaluate the "greenness" of suppliers and/or products for practising sustainability (Lee *et al.* 2012). This phenomenon also inspires other, smaller retailers to apply the same policies. As Lee et al. (2012) found, retailers can change consumers' consciousness and behaviour by directly interacting with them.

Car industry: Battery electric vehicles (EVs) give the option of ultimately zero-carbon and zero-emissions transport. Electrification of the car means a disruptive change to the existing automotive and energy business models in all sections of the value chain. Nieuwenhuis (2018) argues that new electric vehicle (EV) business models need to extend beyond the boundaries of the business itself, including both context and environment. EV business models are affected by regulatory-based incentives and thus operate in artificial market conditions. As Nieuwenhuis (2018) states, these business models are dynamic and different private and public sector players are still exploring what their respective roles should be in future EV business models.

Green food: The markets for green or sustainable food have grown globally since the 1990's, and currently, in many countries, supermarkets have a central role as resellers of sustainable green food products. They buy from global distributors as well as from farms and local producers. The alternative natural food and grocery stores and farmers' markets have been partly required to take a smaller role, due to smaller capacity and the growing consumer demand for green food (Oosterveer, 2007).

Green entrepreneurship as a promoter of SDG 12: Sustainable consumption and production

Green entrepreneurs will be key actors in the business ecosystem and aid in the implementation of more sustainable production processes that will, in turn, support the sustainable consumption behaviour of greening consumers. When targeting sustainable consumption and production, especially the development of resource and energy efficiency, and more sustainable infrastructures are critical. With green entrepreneurship, economic development will be implemented so that environmental and social costs are reduced, and economic competitiveness is built more on the basis of sustainable criteria, including environmental and social criteria, in addition to economic sustainability. The advancement of green entrepreneurship will thus also help to develop more green and sustainable workplaces and a better work-life environment for the workers.

1.3. Conclusion

The green economy creates opportunities for entrepreneurs, and in order to take advantage of this, the employability of young people and women should be improved by providing targeted, up-to-date training in the new skills required in the green economy and by creating incentive mechanisms to encourage green entrepreneurship (Demuth, 2015). Although efforts are being made by the government and concerned individuals at various levels to encourage green entrepreneurship, more needs to be done to ensure green entrepreneurial development and compliance with the green economy transition to see Kogi State and Nigeria in general thrive economically, socially and environmentally.

1.4. Recommendations

It has been revealed, among other things, in the course of this work that green entrepreneurship has great potential to promote economic opportunities and influence sustainable development. The research therefore recommends that:

1. Further research and development in the area of green entrepreneurship should be carried out to foster our sustainable environment, sustainable development and economic growth.
2. The government and policymakers should invest in green entrepreneurship because it comes with green innovations, which provide green jobs and aid the nation in sustaining its economic growth. Convening seminars for those interested in green entrepreneurship, including farmers, educational blogging, and the use of green poems, are also other ways to sensitise the people about the effects of environmental challenges (Anabaraonye *et al.* 2019).

3. Existing entrepreneurs should comply with green processes, which could create opportunities for other green businesses for more sustainable livelihood initiatives.
4. Seminars, workshops, and Public orientation programs should be organised regularly to enlighten the populace on the benefits of the green economy and green entrepreneurship for sustainable development in Nigeria.
5. The government should put in place the necessary policies and the enabling entrepreneurial environment to encourage entrepreneurs in the green sector. They should encourage and support green innovations and businesses, as well as help to educate people on the need to go into green businesses.

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